

STUDY ON FUNCTIONING OF SELENIUM TESTING TOOL

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ABSTRACT

Automation testing tool is evolving field which provide maximum benefits to the software market by minimalizing efforts as well as cost for testing a software. In today's word, there are numerous programming languages namely Java, python, Ruby, C++ etc. and rare automated testing tools which works on most of languages. So selenium brings all these common language to the market. Now a tester can opt any of these languages to work with. There are a lot more features of selenium which makes it comfortable for tester to execute a test cross such as it supports multiple platforms and browsers. Selenium is one such tool which is an open source so it's easy to install and even cost effective tool. There are many review papers regarding automation tools and selenium but none was able to provide all the specified features of selenium, which is an open source so its demand in market is very high from the time it was developed. The basic goal of this review Paper is to provide a brief knowledge of the automation testing tool which becomes a crucial part of the institutions, organizations and industries such as e-commerce, travel, biotech, pharmaceuticals etc. This review paper focuses on filling the gaps between few research papers by highlighting the need and features of selenium.

Keywords: Automation Testing Tools, selenium, Selenium IDE, Selenium RC, Selenium Grid, Selenium WebDriver.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this growing era Software Testing becomes most important part of software development. Software testing is the method of evaluating software to find errors or bugs in it. It is used to check the quality of a developed software. It gives us the result by differentiating expected and the actual result.

Software testing can be done in two ways namely, manual software testing and automation software testing. Manual software testing requires human interaction with the software while automation software testing composed of testing the software product using automation tools.

Figure 1-Components Of Software Testing

Manual software testing tool follows a written test plan.

Limitations of Manual software testing is:-

1. Very time consuming

2. Takes a lot of effort
3. Not reusable
4. Expensive than open source testing tool

Automation testing tools is an important part of software due to its advancement like execution of speed of test cases, efficiency, and reliability etc. automation tool is an essential part of industries to save both time and money.

In this method, tester runs script on testing tools only. It includes white box testing as well as black box testing.

1) Black box testing: - it is mainly based on output requirements. It does not concerned with the internal detailed or structure of a software production. It does not require any knowledge of internal structure for coding in programming.

2) White box testing: - it is also known as glass box testing or clear box testing. It is the process of giving input to system and checking how system processes the input for output. It is applicable at integration unit and system levels of software testing process. In this bugs could be found before trouble.

3) Gray box testing: - it is the testing strategy that consists of the combination of both white and black box testing. It means when internal information is also required but in small ratio.

Automation testing tools can further be subdivided into open source testing tools and commercial test tools.

- Open source testing tools are the tools which are free for developers or users and these can be easily downloaded and install on PC for free of cost. Example is selenium.
- Commercial test tools are the tools which are not available freely and requires payment for using them to test the software. Example is QTP.

Advantages of automation testing tools:-

1. Increases test execution speed (execution speed can be calculated by taking total test run time of each script that is start test run time addition to end test run time.)
2. Reliable as chances of error is least
3. Repeatable
4. Programmable
5. Comprehensive
6. Reusable
7. Automates steps of manual testing by automation tools
8. Time saving
9. Requires less efforts

Some examples of automated testing tools are as follows:-

1) QTP or quick test professional

QTP is used for functionality test.it is easy to use as technical as well as non-technical individual can excess. It is mainly a graphical interface record playback automation testing tool. It is also a regression testing tool which helps the tester to test a software or to execute a test cross. HP QTP support to automate a 'Non-UI' based test cases such as file system operation and database testing. It has Microsoft operating system. It supports Firefox Chrome, IE 6, 7, 8 and 10. It operates on VBscript. It is not a free of cost testing tools because it is a commercial type testing tool.

2) TestComplete

TestComplete is a commercial type functional automated testing tool so a tester has to pay to use it. It provide supports on Microsoft windows operating system. TestComplete mainly supports IE, Firefox and Google Chrome browser. It provides a good support of many programming languages such as VBscript, JavaScript, and C++ Delphi script #script. It supports both web applications and windows applications. It developed by SmartBear Software. TestComplete supports Selenium WebDriver tests formed in JUnit. TestNG.

3) Watir

Watir is an open source automated testing tool. It is mainly a cross platform operating system. The browsers supported are Internet Explorer, Firefox, Chrome, Safari, and Edge. It runs in headless mode that is HTML Unit. This tool uses Ruby as scripting language. The license name of Watir is BSD. It is a Software testing Framework for web application.it only supports Java, .NET, C# as programming languages.

4) Selenium is basically a portable software testing framework. It is an open source so it is all free of cost for developers to use it as a functional web testing tool.

The paper mainly focuses on the features of selenium which are being used in many fields. Methodology is explained in section III, section IV covers the results and analyses of the study, and section V discusses the future study and Conclusion.

Comparative analysis on different automated testing tools on parameters is shown in table:-

Table 1. Comparison Of Tools On Various Parameters

S. No.	Parameters	Selenium	(QTP)UFT	TestComplete	Watir
1	Release year	2004	1998	1999	2005
2	Test applications	Web Application	Web application	Test Automation Tool	Test Automation Tool
3	Language support	Python, c#, PHP, Ruby, JavaScript	VBScript	VBScript, C#, Jscript, C++, Delphi	Ruby, .Net, C#
4	Test Platform	Cross platform	Windows	Windows	Windows
5	Cost	Free(Open source)	Licensed	Licensed	Free(Open source)
6	License Type	Open Source under Apache 2.0	Proprietary	Proprietary	BSD
7	Platforms	MAC, Linux, Windows	Windows	Windows	MAC, Linux, Windows
8	Browser	Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, Safari, Opera, Internet Explorer, Edge	IE, Firefox, Chrome, Safari, Edge	Firefox, Chrome, Safari, Edge	Firefox, Chrome, Safari, Edge, IE
9	Programming knowledge	Required	Required	Required	Partial
10	Record and Playback	Selenium IDE only	Can only be used in Internet explorer	Support	Support
11	Developer	Jason Huggins	HP	Smartbear	Bret Pettichord, Paul Rogers
12	Extendibility	Limited	Up to only certain extent	Up to only certain extent	Limited
13	Function	For Web Application (not for performance testing)	Web Application, regression, unit, distribute manual	Functional, regression, unit, distribute, load, manual, web	Web Testing
14	Generation of report	Htмл	Htмл, xml	Htмл, xml	Htмл, xml

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Jagannatha et al, [6] proposed an architecture for enhancing the study of selenium by giving an idea about its traits. The model provide the various components of selenium such as Selenium IDE, Selenium WebDriver, Selenium Grid, and their most commonly used commands. This paper gave the comparative study on Automation testing tools such as QTP and Selenium and gave direction to the paper. Selenium is an open and free source add-on for Firefox web browser while QTP is not a free and open source. QTP is a commercial testing tool. Selenium does not supports functional testing, load testing and service monitoring from one test script while HP QTP support all these functions but complex codes are required. Both selenium and QTP requires programming knowledge. Both of these tools provide support to run test in cloud.

Fatini Mobaraya et al, [7] gave the technical analyses of selenium and cypress as functional automation framework for modern web application testing. In this they proposed that there is a significant difference in the results which was based on the parameters such as test execution time, test efficiency and requirement based test coverage. Cypress provides a better test efficiency compared to Selenium as Cypress takes shorter lines of code need to write to complete a test case. Selenium have fast execution for test cases as compared to Cypress. In Selenium, new tab handling can be easily overcome by switching the tab using the keyboard commands but it was not easy for Cypress as Cypress doesn't support multiple tab handling.

In comparative review of the features of automated software testing tools by Heidilyn V. Gamido, Marlon V. Gamido [9], they mention few automated testing tools and their features on different aspects. Chosen software testing tools are:-Selenium, QTP and TestComplete.in this they proposed that, Selenium is an open source and portable testing tool to test web application that supports a Different browser, platforms, and operating system. QTP/UFT (Quick Test Professional/Unified Functional Testing). UFT (formerly called as QTP) is a graphical Interface record-playback automation tool. QTP was developed by HP. Its supporting operating system is Windows. It supports record playback. TestComplete. TestComplete is an application that provide supports automate software quality tests for websites, web applications, and Windows desktop applications. It supports browsers like Chrome, FireFox, Opera and IE.

In Taxonomy of Automated Software Testing Tools given by Kamran Shaukat, Usman Shaukat, Faran Feroz, Shahraiz Kayani, Ali Akbar[11], they proposed the comparison of various tools namely, management tools, loading tools and functional tools on the basis of such as Operating system support, Programming language support, Browser support, License and etc. These tools include Selenium, Ranorex, Soap UI, FitNesse, Appvance, Apache, J meter, HP- QTP, Test Complete and Telerik Test Studio. As mentioned, Selenium license name is Apache 2.0, Watir license is BSD and QTP and TestComplete license is Proprietary. Selenium is an open and free source whereas QTP, Watir and TestComplete are commercial based automated testing tools.

III. METHODOLOGY

Selenium is a free open source test tool which is used for automating the test carried out on different web browsers. It can be easily downloaded and it is used to test web applications only. It does not allow automating other technologies. In selenium, new tab handling can be easily overcome by switching the tab using keyboard command as selenium support multiple tab handling selenium commands is easier to understand for a person who has moderate knowledge in this. It can work equally on revising the code using ways that is defining the code logic within a block and then use it by calling it wherever required. It does not operates at protocol level but works at user level. It can be tested across different browsers which are Chrome, Firefox, and Safari etc. The test can be performed in different operating system platforms such as Windows, Mac, Linux and the selenium test script can be integrated with the tools namely, testNG and Junit for managing test cases and generating reports. Selenium uses JavaScript and iframes to embed the test automation in general in two browser this allows the same test script to be used to test multiple browsers on multiple platforms such as Mac, windows and Linux. Selenium comprises of four components namely, selenium IDE, selenium RC, selenium WebDriver, selenium grid.

- **Selenium IDE** is a Firefox plug-in in which can be used to develop test cases.
- **Selenium RC** allows to write automated web applications UI test in many programming languages.
- **Selenium WebDriver** is developed for better support dynamics web pages where elements of page may change without changing page.

- **Selenium Grid** allows to run test on different machines against different browsers parallel.

1. History of selenium:-

Selenium was developed by Jason Huggins in the year of 2004 as an internal tool. Huggins later associate with the programmer Paul Hermit of ThoughtWorks, and try to develop selenium RC, so mainly it was developed by 2 developers, that are Jason Huggins and Paul hermit. Selenium was an open source from the year it came in market. Selenium RC was the first to found among the selenium WebDriver, selenium grid and selenium IDE.

In 2005, Dan Fabulich and Nelson Sproul developed selenium RC (Remote control) into what it is known for today they are the major reason of giving an idea of about how RC works.

In 2008 Simon Stewart at ThoughtWorks developed the automation tool called the WebDriver.

2. Features of selenium:-

- 1) It is easy to automate testing across web applications.
- 2) It provides data driven testing by using wide range of sources with excel file XML files etc.
- 3) It has a wide variety of language support. It supports C, C++, python, Java, Perl, and Ruby etc.
- 4) To provide greater accessibility in of understandability.
- 5) Selenium script creating time is little slow.
- 6) It allows end users to write and share extensions or other code modifications event to project modified codes.
- 7) In selenium it is easy to implement test cases.
- 8) We can write or perform various test scripts on different platforms light Mac windows and Linux.
- 9) It is easy to understand and is an open source.so no license is required to get it and hence it can be downloaded from its standard website. It is not a paid version it is easy to understand as it is explained in simple words.
- 10) It requires fewer resources as compared to other automation testing tools.
- 11) It gives user a standard set of commands.

3. Components of selenium

- Selenium IDE
- Selenium RC
- Selenium WebDriver
- Selenium Grid

Selenium IDE or integrated development environment

It is primarily a record run tool that a test case developer uses to develop selenium test cases. Test cases written in Selenium IDE can be exported in many programming language like Ruby, Java, python, PHP etc. Selenium IDE is record, debug or edit playback kind of tool which comes as an add-on for Firefox and used as plugin. It is an excellent testing tool for beginners to understand the syntax of selenium WebDriver. It is considered as the simplest framework in selenium suite and easiest to learn and there are fewer command. It can be easily downloaded from selenium standard website. It provides a graphical user interface (GUI) for recording user actions using Firefox only as other browsers are not supported in this. Recorded script can be converted into various programming language and can be executed on various other than Firefox browser too. Commonly used commands in selenium IDE are as follows: - Open command (it allows us to open a page using a URL), Click, ClickAndWait, verifyTitle, assertTitle, VerifyTextPresent, verify Text etc.

Selenium IDE does not support data driven testing.it has limited features while comparing to the WebDriver. WebDriver has extended features such as OpenScript. The advantage of open script is that open script can interact with many browsers.

Limitations of Selenium IDE:-

- A) It does not allow the function keys and special key recording.
- B) It does not allow password encryption.

Selenium RC or remote control

It was developed in 2005 by Dan Fabulich and Nelson Sproul. Selenium RC enables a standalone server using an HTTP proxy. It can be divided into selenium remote server and remote client. It was the first tool of selenium suite. Earlier it was known as JavaScript executor and selenium RC was the tool which made selenium famous in market by that time. It was the first tool which provided support for multiple programming languages. It also supports almost all major vendors of browsers like Firefox, Chrome, internet explorer, etc. using selenium RC we can perform cross browser testing. it allows to write automated web applications UI test in any programming language such as Java, python C#, Ruby, Perl, etc. against any server using an HTTP proxy. By users of so many different languages, it helps in creating more complex tests. It operates in such a way that client libraries communicate with selenium RC server passing each command for execution.

Selenium WebDriver

It comes after selenium RC as it is advancement of selenium RC. It allows to sends directly to browser. Selenium WebDriver addition with selenium RC gives a selenium 2.0. selenium WebDriver directly interacts with the browser unlike selenium RC, which requires a particular server to operate. It is composed of AJAX-based UI elements. It is very helpful in advanced user navigations such as drag-and-drop operation. It allows us to navigate complex pages. Its

Architecture is simpler than selenium RC as it controls the browser from the OS level. It is even faster than selenium RC as it saves the time by not interacting directly with the browser. It can support headless execution unlike selenium RC as it is not interacting with any browser directly. It is capable of testing mobile applications such as iPhone and Android. The commands are taken through client API and are sent to different browsers namely Safari, Mozilla Firefox etc. It uses native operating system functionality to avoid security conflicts and issues.

Selenium Grid

Selenium grid was developed in the year of 2008 by Philippe Hanrigou at Thought Works. By this it become easy to test apps on any number of remote devices via a browser. It allows the test suite to be run in multiple environments simultaneously. This tool helps to run parallel test across different machines and different browsers at the same time as it reduces or minimizes the execution time. It cut down the time required for running test. It allows to execute multiple instances of selenium WebDriver or selenium RC in parallel that uses same code base. It consists of two components namely, a hub or a server and a node or a remote device.

A hub receives command from the WebDriver client. Selenium grid has one server only.

A Node is attached to the hub. It can be one or more in number which can be of any operating system.

4. More about selenium**a. Xebium**

It is made up by the association of the features of 3 frameworks that are Selenium IDE, Selenium WebDriver and FitNesse. With this, integration testing becomes easier. As selenium is a tool for regression testing and FitNesse is a tools for maintainable acceptance testing.

- Operating System:- Windows, MAC, OSX
- Browser:- Android, IOS, Blackberry
- License:-Apache 2.0
- Application support:-Web application
- Language:-Java, C++, Ruby, Python, Delphi, C#
- Cost:- Open source

b. Tellurium

This tool is based on Selenium RC. It is an open source automated testing framework for testing web applications.

- Operating System:- Windows
- Browser:- Android, Blackberry, IOS
- License:- Apache 2.0

- Application support:- Web application
- Language:-Java, Groovy
- Cost:- Open source

IV. RESULTS and ANALYSIS

The features of selenium are given in table as follows:-

Table 2. Features Of Selenium

S. No.	Features	Selenium
1	Release year	2004
2	Test applications	Web Application
3	Language support	Python, c#, PHP, Ruby, JavaScript
4	Test Platform	Cross platform
5	Cost	Free (Open source)
6	License Type	Open Source under Apache 2.0
7	Average Execution Time	153.866sec
8	Script creating time	Slow
9	Platforms	MAC, Linus, Windows
10	Components	Selenium IDE, Selenium RC, Selenium WebDriver, Selenium Grid
11	Browser	Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, Safari, Opera, Internet Explorer, Edge
12	Programming knowledge	Required
13	Record and Playback	Selenium IDE only
14	Test run in cloud	Yes
15	Test development environment	Need separate environment
16	Defect Management Reporting	Not available
17	Schedule Execution	With complex codes
18	Support Dialogue Box	Support partially
19	Multiple tab handling	Yes
20	Developer	Jason Huggins
21	Extendibility	Limited
22	Function	For Web Application (not for performance testing)
23	Test Development environment requirements	Wide range of IDEs could be used namely, Eclipse, Net beans, Visual Studio etc.
24	Object identification	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Automatic UI object identification - No 2. Use of Xpath expression, robust object identification- No
25	Generation of report	Html

Limitations of selenium

1. In handling dynamics elements image synthesis, page loads & pop-up windows in current web applications.
2. It only supports browser applications.
3. It provides partial support for dialog boxes.

4. It does not support object identification like automatic UI object synchronization as well as use of Xpath expression and robust identification.
5. It has no official technical support as it is an open source.
6. It does not allow uploading of files from local machines.
7. IT is not support performing mobile automation on its own.

V. CONCLUSION

As software testing field is evolving, features as well as cost of a product cannot be taken as for granted. Presently in market there are numerous automation software testing tools are available but selenium is still one such tool consider to cross minds first as it is free of cost and is it has some very significant features. To study about selenium we have target twenty four frequently used characteristics to check the performance such as Test applications, Language support, Test Platform, Cost, License Type, Average Execution Time, Script creating time etc. Selenium showed great results in maximum of them. This review paper concludes that this field still requires a thorough research to improvise in quality of version of selenium to overcome its limitations and extend it more in features.

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